

***k*-Coverage: Improved Heuristics for the *k*-Center, *k*-Max-Min-Dispersion, and Multi-Objective Facility Location Problems**

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Abstract.

Facility location problems are a core class of discrete optimization problems with applications well beyond physical ‘facilities’. This paper – motivated by the active learning task in machine learning – focuses on the *k*-Center (minimizing the maximum distance), the *k*-Median (minimizing the sum of distances), the *k*-Max-Min-Dispersion (maximizing the minimum separation), and the *k*-Sum-Min-Dispersion (maximizing the sum of minimum separation distances) problems. Recent active learning literature relies on the 2-approximation greedy algorithm for the *k*-Center, and a respective $\frac{1}{2}$ -approximation greedy algorithm for *k*-Max-Min-Dispersion. We propose two novel heuristic algorithms; one for the *k*-Center problem and one for the *k*-Max-Min-Dispersion problem that, as shown in an experimental study, reduce the optimality gap of those greedy algorithms by more than 50% for *k*-Center and over 80% for *k*-Max-Min-Dispersion on 800 synthetic problems with known optima, and improve performance on larger instances where exact solutions are unavailable. Our *k*-Center specific algorithm is less sensitive to outliers and simultaneously improves on both *k*-Center and *k*-Median objectives. A key advantage of our approach is its flexibility: with minor modifications, the heuristics can target a wide range of facility-location objectives. We conduct a limited experimental study on active learning instances and show that improved *k*-Center solutions do not yield better active learning solutions, suggesting that a better *k*-Center objective does not imply empirical success, contrary to recent literature. We further prove a theoretical result showing a tighter bound on the active learning core-set loss function is provided by the *k*-Median optimal solution, and show, for a few datasets, that *k*-Median optimal labeling solutions indeed have higher test accuracy on the active learning problem than other facility location objectives.

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1. Introduction

Facility location problems form an important class of discrete optimization. Many problems can be thought of in terms of facility location, beyond simply placing physical “facilities.” The motivation for this study is the use of facility location objectives in the active learning literature. Active learning is a problem that arises in the presence of many unlabeled, but expensive to label, observations in machine learning. As we show here, the *k*-Median problem solution provides, theoretically, a better selection of observations to label, in terms of leading to tighter (lower) bound on the loss function. Still, prior work by Sener and Savarese (2018) demonstrates that heuristics for the *k*-Center problem perform better, in terms of accuracy, than the heuristic algorithm of Har-Peled and Kushal (2005) used to solve the *k*-Median problem.

In this work, we provide alternative heuristic methods for relevant variants of the facility location problem: the *k*-Center problem, which seeks to minimize the maximum distance from any “customer” to the nearest of the *k* opened facilities, the *k*-Max-Min-Dispersion problem, which aims to select *k* facilities so that the minimum distance between any two is maximized, and the *k*-Median problem that seeks to minimize the sum of distances from customers to their nearest opened facilities.

Based on a limited empirical analysis shown here, in the context of active learning, the relative success of the k -Center greedy solution is not due to closeness to optimality of the k -Center objective. It is rather related to the use of the greedy algorithm, Gonzalez (1985), which greedily maximizes the distances between the facilities selected, without consideration of the distances to the customers. In that sense this greedy algorithm is identical (except for the seed starting point) to the greedy algorithm for the k -Max-Min-Dispersion by Ravi et al. (1991) and produces the same solution.

We introduce here, two methods, called *Coverage k -Center* and *Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Dispersion* that are guaranteed to provide better solutions than the respective greedy solutions to these problems. Furthermore, these can serve to provide heuristic solutions for other objective functions such as k -Median and k -Sum-Min-Dispersion (defined in Section 2). The coverage method is useful when the objective focuses on customers and their relationship to facilities whereas the anti-coverage method is useful when only the relationship between facilities are relevant.

We present here an empirical study. The experiments are run on datasets that include both synthetic (uniform and clustered) datasets as well as classical machine learning datasets. The study demonstrates meaningful improvements in the stated objectives of both the k -Center and the k -Max-Min-Dispersion problems. Furthermore, we show that our coverage heuristic provides solution sets that have simultaneously better k -Center and k -Median objectives than those of the greedy k -Center solutions. Yet, while the k -Center and k -Max-Min-Dispersion solutions, attained by the new methods, have more favorable characteristics, this does not translate to improvements in active learning. Our results imply that the performance of greedy k -Center on active learning cannot be attributed to the quality of solutions attained for the k -Center or k -Median objectives. This establishes the need for further research to understand the underlying causes for the greedy k -Center's good performance in practice for active learning.

Paper Overview. The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we present formally the facility location problems studied here. Section 3 describes both existing heuristic algorithms for the problems and the newly introduced coverage and anti-coverage methods. Section 4 reports on the experimental results, on the generation of the datasets and on the comparison of the existing (greedy) algorithms to our new coverage and anti-coverage algorithms. The comparison is in terms of the attained objective values for: k -Center, k -Median, k -Max-Min-Dispersion, and k -Sum-Min-Dispersion. Section 5 describes a brief experimental study of the effect of using the objectives of k -Center or k -Median on the accuracy attained for the active learning problem. We compare the accuracy of label-sets generated by optimal solvers, the greedy k -Center algorithm, the coverage algorithm, and random selection.

2. The Studied Facility Location Problems

The k -Center problem

The k -Center problem aims to select k facility locations to minimize the maximum distance between any customer and its nearest facility. The problem is defined on a complete graph $G = (V, E)$ where V denotes the set of potential facility locations that include the customer locations. For each pair of nodes $i, j \in V$, d_{ij} denotes the metric distance between the pair (i.e., it satisfies the triangle inequality). The objective is to choose a subset $S \subseteq V$ of k facilities that minimizes the maximum distance between any customer and its closest facility:

$$\min_{S \subseteq V, |S|=k} \max_{v \in V} \min_{s \in S} d_{vs}. \quad (1)$$

The decision version of the k -Center problem is as follows: Given a radius $R > 0$ and an integer k , does there exist a subset $S \subseteq V$ of k “facilities” such that every customer lies within distance R of at least one open facility:

$$\exists S \subseteq V, |S| = k \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \max_{v \in V} \min_{s \in S} d_{vs} \leq R ? \quad (2)$$

Equivalently, for each potential facility $s \in V$, define its R -coverage set

$$C_s(R) := \{ v \in V : d_{vs} \leq R \} \quad (3)$$

The decision problem is equivalent to selecting k facilities whose coverage sets collectively cover all customers:

$$\exists S \subseteq V, |S| = k \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \bigcup_{s \in S} C_s(R) = V ? \quad (4)$$

The k -Center problem is NP-hard (Kariv and Hakimi 1979) and even for metric distances, achieving a δ -approximation for any $\delta < 2$ is NP-hard (Hsu and Nemhauser 1979). A best-possible approximation algorithm for the k -Center problem was first proposed by Hochbaum and Shmoys (Hochbaum and Shmoys 1985), using ideas related to coverage similar to our algorithms. Gonzalez (Gonzalez 1985) introduces the greedy algorithm, *Greedy k -Center*. The pseudo-code for Greedy k -Center is provided in Section 3 as Algorithm 1.

The k -Median

The k -Median problem defined on a complete graph $G = (V, E)$ with distances (not necessarily metric) is:

$$\min_{S \subseteq V, |S|=k} \sum_{v \in V} \min_{s \in S} d_{vs}. \quad (5)$$

The k -Median is obviously equivalent to the average (or expected) k -Median where the objective is $\min_{S \subseteq V, |S| \leq k} \frac{1}{|V|} \sum_{v \in V} \min_{s \in S} d_{vs}$. k -Median can be viewed as the summation version of the k -Center problem, where instead of focusing on the worst-case distance the focus is on the average distance.

The k -Max-Min-Dispersion

The k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem is defined on a complete graph $G = (V, E)$, with d_{ij} denoting the metric distance between i and j . The objective is to select a subset $S \subseteq V$ of k facilities so as to maximize the minimum pairwise distance among the chosen facilities.

$$\max_{S \subseteq V, |S|=k} \min_{i, j \in S, i \neq j} d_{ij} \quad (6)$$

The k -Max-Min-Dispersion decision problem is defined for a given distance threshold $R \geq 0$ and an integer k . The question is whether there exists a subset $S \subseteq V$ of k “facilities” such that every pair of opened facilities is at least distance R apart:

$$\exists S \subseteq V, |S| = k \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \min_{i, j \in S, i \neq j} d_{ij} \geq R ? \quad (7)$$

Equivalently, for each potential facility $s \in V$, define its *strict* R -coverage set

$$C_s^<(R) := \{ v \in V : d_{sv} < R \} \quad (8)$$

The decision problem is then equivalent to selecting k facilities whose strict coverage sets contain a selected facility if and only if it is the strict coverage set defined for that selected facility:

$$\exists S \subseteq V, |S| = k \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \bigcup_{s \in S} (C_s^<(R) \setminus \{s\}) = \emptyset ? \quad (9)$$

The k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem is NP-hard (Erkut 1990). For the metric case of k -Max-Min-Dispersion, a δ -approximation for any $\delta > \frac{1}{2}$ is NP-hard (Ravi et al. 1991). A greedy best-possible approximation algorithm was given by Ravi, Rosenkrantz, and Tayi (Ravi et al. 1991), *Greedy k-Max-Min-Dispersion*. Notably, aside from the choice of the initial facilities, the Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion is structurally identical to the Greedy k -Center algorithm. For brevity, we omit its pseudo-code.

The k -Sum-Min-Dispersion

The k -Sum-Min-Dispersion problem defined on a complete graph $G = (V, E)$ with distances (not necessarily metric) is:

$$\max_{S \subseteq V, |S|=k} \sum_{i \in S} \min_{j \in S \setminus \{i\}} d_{ij}. \quad (10)$$

The k -Sum-Min-Dispersion is obviously equivalent to the average k -Sum-Min-Dispersion where the objective is $\max_{S \subseteq V, |S|=k} \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{i \in S} \min_{j \in S \setminus \{i\}} d_{ij}$. k -Sum-Min-Dispersion can be viewed as the summation version of the k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem, where instead of focusing on the worst-case distance the focus is on the average distance. In that sense the relationship is analogous to that between k -Median and k -Center.

3. Description of the Algorithms

Greedy k -Center Algorithm

The core principle of the Greedy k -Center of Gonzalez (Gonzalez 1985) (Algorithm 1), is to iteratively select the facility farthest from the current set of chosen facilities.

Algorithm 1 Greedy k -Center

```

1: Input: Distances  $d_{ij}$ , Customers / Facilities  $V$ , # of facilities  $k$ 
2: Output: Set of selected facilities  $S$  and the max distance to a customer  $r^*$ 
3:  $s_1 \in V$  ▷  $s_1$  arbitrary
4:  $S \leftarrow \{s_1\}$ 
5:  $\text{minDist}[v] \leftarrow d_{v,s_1} \quad \forall v \in V$ 
6: for  $i = 2$  to  $k$  do
7:    $s_i \leftarrow \arg \max_{v \in V} \text{minDist}[v]$ 
8:    $S \leftarrow S \cup \{s_i\}$ 
9:    $\text{minDist}[v] \leftarrow \min(\text{minDist}[v], d_{v,s_i}) \quad \forall v \in V$ 
10: end for
11:  $r^* \leftarrow \max_{v \in V} \text{minDist}[v]$ 
12: return  $S, r^*$ 

```

The Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion Algorithm

The description of this $\frac{1}{2}$ -approximation algorithm, Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion, of Ravi, Rosenkrantz, and Tayi is omitted. This is because the only difference from Greedy k -Center is that the first two facilities are chosen to be the pair farthest from each other, rather than selected arbitrarily.

The Coverage k -Center Algorithm

We introduce the first of our algorithms here, the Coverage k -Center algorithm. To mitigate the sensitivity to outliers of the Greedy k -Center algorithm and to actively consider the location of customers, the coverage algorithm iterates over a set of reasonable candidate radii R and applies the greedy algorithm for k -Coverage, introduced by Hochbaum and Pathria (Hochbaum and Pathria 1998). The k -Coverage algorithm is a heuristic for the maximum k -Coverage, which is to maximize the number of nodes that are covered by k sets. Here those candidate sets are the coverage sets for a given radius R . The radius R is selected by first running the Greedy k -Center algorithm and use the radius solution delivered by that algorithm, r^* . Since the Greedy k -Center is a 2-approximation algorithm, we know that the optimal radius solution must reside in the range $[\frac{1}{2}r^*, r^*]$. We choose a number of equally spaced radii values in this interval. This number n_{radii} is a parameter provided by the user. The k -Coverage algorithm is run for each of these candidate values. In case all nodes are covered with strictly less than k facilities we augment the set to k by adding, one at a time, the furthest facility from the existing ones.

This Coverage k -Center algorithm is similar in spirit to that proposed by Hochbaum and Shmoys (Hochbaum and Shmoys 1985). While the Hochbaum and Shmoys algorithm checks the coverage for all values of the distances in the graph, standing for R , and reporting the smallest radius for which k facilities suffice to cover all nodes, the Coverage k -Center algorithm checks all candidate values in $[\frac{1}{2}r^*, r^*]$ and produces n_{radii} solution sets from which the “best” one is selected, according to the desired objective. The Coverage k -Center algorithm can then have significant computational advantages compared to the Hochbaum and Shmoys algorithm due to not needing to check all possible candidate radii. In this pseudocode the desired objective is the k -Center objective.

Algorithm 2 Coverage k -Center

```

1: Input: Distances  $d_{ij}$ , Customers / Facilities  $V$ , # of facilities  $k$ , # of radii  $n_{\text{radii}}$ 
2: Output: Selected facility set  $S^*$ , objective radius  $r^*$ 
3:  $S^*, r^* \leftarrow$  Greedy  $k$ -Center( $d_{ij}, V, k$ )
4:  $r_{\min}, r_{\max} \leftarrow 0.5 \cdot r^*, r^*$ 
5: for  $i = 1$  to  $n_{\text{radii}}$  do
6:    $S, C \leftarrow \emptyset, \emptyset$ 
7:    $r \leftarrow r_{\min} + \frac{(i-1)(r_{\max}-r_{\min})}{n_{\text{radii}}-1}$ 
8:    $C_v(r) \leftarrow \{j \in V \mid d_{jv} \leq r\}, \forall v \in V$ 
9:   for  $j = 1$  to  $k$  do
10:    if  $C \neq V$  then
11:       $s_j \leftarrow \arg \max_{v \in V} |C_v(r) \setminus C|$ 
12:    else
13:       $s_j \leftarrow \arg \max_{v \in V} \min_{s \in S} d_{vs}$ 
14:    end if
15:     $S, C \leftarrow S \cup \{s_j\}, C \cup C_{s_j}$ 
16:  end for
17:   $r_{\text{obj}} \leftarrow \max_{v \in V} \min_{s \in S} d_{sv}$ 
18:  if  $r_{\text{obj}} < r^*$  then
19:     $r^*, S^* \leftarrow r_{\text{obj}}, S$ 
20:  end if
21: end for
22: return  $S^*, r^*$ 

```

The Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Dispersion Algorithm

The Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Dispersion is similar to the Coverage k -Center, with the following exceptions:

- The range of radii checked is determined by the solution of the Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion algorithm, r^* and then set to be $[r^*, 2r^*]$. This range of radii is chosen since the Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion algorithm is a $\frac{1}{2}$ -approximation algorithm implying this range is guaranteed to contain the true optimum.,
 - The facility with minimal additive coverage is selected at each iteration instead of the maximal additive coverage, and only uncovered facilities are considered.
 - The “best” objective is now the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective.
- The procedure is formally described in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3 Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Dispersion

```

1: Input: Distances  $d_{ij}$ , Customers / Facilities  $V$ , # of facilities  $k$ , # of radii  $n_{\text{radii}}$ 
2: Output: Selected facility set  $S^*$ , objective radius  $r^*$ 
3:  $S^*, r^* \leftarrow$  Greedy  $k$ -Max-Min-Dispersion( $d_{ij}, V, k$ )
4:  $r_{\min} r_{\max} \leftarrow r^*, 2 \cdot r^*$ 
5: for  $i = 1$  to  $n_{\text{radii}}$  do
6:    $S, C \leftarrow \emptyset, \emptyset$ 
7:    $r \leftarrow r_{\min} + \frac{(i-1)(r_{\max}-r_{\min})}{n_{\text{radii}}-1}$ 
8:    $C_v(r) \leftarrow \{j \in V \mid d_{jv} \leq r\}, \forall v \in V$ 
9:   for  $j = 1$  to  $k$  do
10:    if  $V \neq C$  then
11:       $s_j \leftarrow \arg \min_{v \in V \setminus C} |C_v(r) \setminus C|$ 
12:    else
13:       $s_j \leftarrow \arg \max_{v \in V} \min_{s \in S} d_{vs}$ 
14:    end if
15:     $S, C \leftarrow S \cup \{s_j\}, C \cup C_{s_j}$ 
16:  end for
17:   $r_{\text{obj}} \leftarrow \min_{i,j \in S, i \neq j} d_{ij}$ 
18:  if  $r_{\text{obj}} > r^*$  then
19:     $r^*, S^* \leftarrow r_{\text{obj}}, S$ 
20:  end if
21: end for
22: return  $S^*, r^*$ 

```

4. Experimental Results

To evaluate the practical performance of our heuristics, we conduct experiments across three distinct scenarios. In all experiments, we evaluate the k -Center problem using 11 (10 equal sub-intervals plus the endpoints) candidate radii and the k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem using 51 (50 equal sub-intervals plus the endpoints) candidate radii. Empirically, we find that checking these many radii generates meaningful improvements; if even larger improvements are desired more radii can be checked.

The first two scenarios involve two distinct methods of synthetically generating small datasets, allowing us to control problem parameters, systematically repeat experiments, and compute the exact optimal solution using integer programming. The first synthetic generation methodology generates a uniform distribution of facilities and the second generates clusters. These controlled experiments provide a clear benchmark for assessing both solution quality and algorithmic behavior. We restrict our synthetic experiments to these small datasets so that the true optimal solution can be readily calculated. The third scenario considers real-world applications, in which the goal is to select representative or diverse samples from large datasets. This setting highlights the practical

utility of our heuristics, demonstrating their ability to scale to large problem instances where exact optimization is computationally infeasible.

4.1. Synthetic Uniform Data Sets

The first set of synthetically generated results is based on points simulated in the unit square $\{x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid 0 \leq x_1 \leq 1, 0 \leq x_2 \leq 1\}$, with $N = |V| \in \{100, 300\}$ potential facility locations sampled uniformly at random, and $k \in \{5, 10, 15\}$ for $N = 100$ and $k = 15$ for $N = 300$. This controlled, two-dimensional setup allows us to systematically evaluate the performance of our algorithms across multiple trials. To obtain meaningful comparisons, we repeat this dataset generation process 100 times for each setup. For each trial, we compute the optimal k -Center or k -Max-Min-Dispersion solution using Gurobi (Gurobi Optimization, LLC 2024) (reported as **Exact k -Center** and **Exact k -Max-Min-Dispersion**), and then compare the results of the different heuristics to the optimal benchmark. This methodology enables us to quantify both the average performance gains of our methods and their consistency relative to known optimal solutions.

The results for the k -Center problem on this data-generating procedure are as follows. In Table 1, we report the performance of Greedy k -Center and our proposed heuristic, Coverage k -Center, averaged over 100 instances per setup. To make the results comparable across problem instances, we normalize the objective values so that Exact k -Center always achieves an objective value of 1 for both the k -Center objective and the k -Median objective. In the case of the k -Center objective, this means the reported values are the average optimality gap.

Figure 1 further shows the normalized objective values for each of the 100 problem instances for $N = 100$ and $k = 10$. Under this dataset generation setup, we find that in all 100 cases Coverage k -Center outperforms Greedy k -Center on the k -Center objective and these facilities placements by Coverage k -Center almost always simultaneously achieve better values of the k -Median objective. Notably, in one instance Coverage k -Center identified a near-optimal solution for a problem instance where Greedy k -Center produced a solution approximately 1.6 times worse than the true optimum. On average, Coverage k -Center achieves a 16.8% improvement on the k -Center (primary) objective and a 12.8% improvement on the k -median (secondary) objective for the case of $N = 100$ and $k = 10$. These results indicate that our method not only finds more optimal k -Center solutions but also better placements for multi-objective facility location problems. The results are robust to different choices of N and k as demonstrated in Table 1.

We now examine the results for the k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem. Table 2 reports the average performance of the Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion heuristic and our proposed one, Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Dispersion, benchmarked to the true optimal k -Max-Min-Dispersion solution. To make the results comparable across problem instances, we again normalize the objective values so that Exact k -Max-Min-Dispersion always achieves an objective value of 1 for both the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective and the k -Sum-Min-Dispersion objective. In the case of the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective, this then corresponds to the average optimality gap. Figure 2 plots results per instance for the case of $N = 100$ and $k = 10$. Similar to the k -Center case, we observe a consistent improvements in the objective, with our heuristic identifying many true optimal solutions. However, in this setting, there is no meaningful change in the other objective k -Sum-Min-Dispersion. For the case of $N = 100$ and $k = 10$ our heuristic achieves an average improvement of 17% on the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective, yielding solutions that are, on average, within 2% of the true optimum. Consistent with the k -Center case Table 2 demonstrates the k -Sum-Min-Dispersion results are robust to the choice of N and k .

Our experimental results demonstrate that, under our uniform synthetic dataset generation methodology, the proposed heuristics consistently yield substantially improved solutions for both the k -Center and k -Max-Min-Dispersion problems.

Table 1 Uniform Data Sets: Normalized performance of algorithms on the k -Center objective and the k -Median objective (averaged across random seeds). Smaller is better.

Setup	Method	k -Center (Exact k -Center := 1)	k -Median (Exact k -Center := 1)
$N = 100, k = 5$	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Center	1.474	1.324
	Coverage k -Center	1.098	1.021
$N = 100, k = 10$	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Center	1.369	1.202
	Coverage k -Center	1.134	1.050
$N = 100, k = 15$	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Center	1.288	1.143
	Coverage k -Center	1.097	1.054
$N = 300, k = 15$	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Center	1.349	1.178
	Coverage k -Center	1.179	1.076

Comparison of Greedy vs. Coverage Heuristics on the k -Center Problem ($N=100, k=10$)
(All values normalized s.t. Exact k -Center := 1 for each instance and objective)**Figure 1** Comparison of the Greedy k -Center and Coverage k -Center heuristics on the k -Center problem. All objective values are normalized by the objective achieved by Exact k -Center. Observations below the dashed “Equal Performance” line indicate instances where the Coverage k -Center heuristic outperforms Greedy k -Center.

4.2. Synthetic Cluster Data Sets

To further test the robustness of our methods, we now consider a second approach for generating synthetic datasets. This second setup is designed to create structured, clustered spatial distributions in two dimensions. We begin by sampling five cluster centers uniformly at random from the square region $[0, 10]^2$. Each of the $N = |V| \in \{100, 300\}$ candidate locations is then assigned to one of these centers and drawn from a two-dimensional Gaussian distribution centered at its assigned cluster, with a standard deviation of 1 along each axis. This construction produces datasets with clearly defined but partially overlapping clusters, providing a more structured and realistic spatial

Table 2 Uniform Data Sets: Normalized performance of algorithms on the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective and the k -Sum-Min-Dispersion objective (averaged across random seeds). Larger is better.

Setup	Method	k -Max-Min-Disp.	k -Sum-Min-Disp.
$N = 100, k = 5$	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.964	1.004
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.992	1.006
$N = 100, k = 10$	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.834	0.974
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.981	0.991
$N = 100, k = 15$	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.824	0.934
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.978	0.987
$N = 300, k = 15$	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.773	0.899
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.973	0.982

Comparison of Greedy vs. Anti-Coverage Heuristics on the k -Max-Min-Dispersion Problem ($N=100, k=10$)
 (All values normalized s.t. Exact k -Max-Min-Dispersion := 1 for each instance and objective)

Figure 2 Comparison of the Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion and Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Dispersion heuristics on the k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem. All objective values are normalized by the objective achieved by Exact k -Max-Min-Dispersion. Observations above the dashed “Equal Performance” line indicate instances where the Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Dispersion heuristic outperforms Greedy k -Max-Min-Dispersion.

configuration. We again generate 100 independent datasets per setup using this methodology and test for $k \in \{5, 10, 15\}$ for $N = 100$ and $k = 15$ for $N = 300$.

Our results under this clustered synthetic dataset generation methodology are reported in Tables 3 and 4, normalized in the same way as in our first set of experiments. We observe that the performance trends are consistent with those seen in the first synthetic setup, including robustness to the choice of N and k . For the k -Center problem with $N = 100$ and $k = 10$, our heuristic achieves an average improvement of 19% on the k -Center objective and 20% on the k -Median objective. For the k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem with $N = 100$ and $k = 10$, we observe a 14% improvement in the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective. To further validate these findings under more general distributions, we next evaluate our heuristics on standard real-world datasets.

Table 3 Cluster Data Sets: Normalized performance of algorithms on the k -Center objective and the k -Median objective (averaged across random seeds). Smaller is better.

Setup	Method	k -Center	k -Median
$N = 100, k = 5$	Exact k-Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Center	1.529	1.521
	Coverage k-Center	1.133	1.026
$N = 100, k = 10$	Exact k-Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Center	1.394	1.279
	Coverage k-Center	1.118	1.021
$N = 100, k = 15$	Exact k-Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Center	1.321	1.184
	Coverage k-Center	1.112	1.035
$N = 300, k = 15$	Exact k-Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Center	1.396	1.236
	Coverage k-Center	1.210	1.016

Table 4 Cluster Data Sets: Normalized performance of algorithms on the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective and the k -Sum-Min-Dispersion objective (averaged across random seeds). Larger is better.

Setup	Method	k -Max-Min-Disp.	k -Sum-Min-Disp.
$N = 100, k = 5$	Exact k-Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.877	0.960
	Anti-Coverage k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.986	1.001
$N = 100, k = 10$	Exact k-Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.865	0.961
	Anti-Coverage k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.985	0.996
$N = 100, k = 15$	Exact k-Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.863	0.955
	Anti-Coverage k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.983	0.992
$N = 300, k = 15$	Exact k-Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.845	0.930
	Anti-Coverage k-Max-Min-Disp.	0.972	0.984

4.3. Real-World Data Sets

We report results for the following datasets where d is the dimension of the dataset, $|V|$ is the number of candidate locations, c is the number of unique classes, and $k \in \{3c, 6c\}$ is the number of facilities:

Table 5 Summary of datasets and parameters.

Dataset	d	$ V $	c	k
Iris (Fisher 1936)	4	150	3	{9, 18}
Heart Disease (Janosi et al. 1989)	28	303	5	{15, 30}
MNIST (LeCun et al. 2010)	784	70000	10	{30, 60}
CIFAR10 (Krizhevsky 2009)	3072	60000	10	{30, 60}

We are able to calculate the exact values for Iris and Heart Disease, but not for MNIST and CIFAR10. The results of our tests are presented in Table 6 for the k -Center problem and Table 7 for the k -Max-Min-Dispersion problem. We find that the results from earlier synthetic experiments are consistent with what we observe on these datasets. Our heuristic can meaningfully improve objective values for both the k -Center and k -Max-Min-Dispersion. In the case of k -Center we also find that when the selected facilities are evaluated on the k -Median objective there is a significant improvement compared to the Greedy k -Center algorithm.

Table 6 Performance of algorithms on the k -Center objective and the k -Median objective (normalized so best value equals 1). Smaller is better.

Dataset	Method	k -Center	k -Median
Iris ($k = 9$)	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Center	1.583	1.422
	Coverage k -Center	1.159	1.010
Iris ($k = 18$)	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Center	1.344	1.330
	Coverage k -Center	1.054	1.007
Heart Disease ($k = 15$)	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.030
	Greedy k -Center	1.198	1.241
	Coverage k -Center	1.063	1.000
Heart Disease ($k = 30$)	Exact k -Center	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Center	1.262	1.194
	Coverage k -Center	1.070	1.040
MNIST ($k = 30$)	Greedy k -Center	1.056	1.124
	Coverage k -Center	1.000	1.000
MNIST ($k = 60$)	Greedy k -Center	1.061	1.140
	Coverage k -Center	1.000	1.000
CIFAR10 ($k = 30$)	Greedy k -Center	1.124	1.139
	Coverage k -Center	1.000	1.000
CIFAR10 ($k = 60$)	Greedy k -Center	1.122	1.152
	Coverage k -Center	1.000	1.000

Across synthetic and real-world datasets, our heuristics consistently improve solution quality for both the k -Center and k -Max-Min-Dispersion problems. Further, in the case of k -Center, we are able to generate facility sets with better characteristics for the k -Median objective as well. These gains hold across uniform, clustered, and high-dimensional datasets for different choices of k , demonstrating both robustness and scalability. Overall, our methods produce solutions that are not only closer to the optimal objectives but also more naturally distributed.

5. Brief Experimental Study on Active Learning

The goal of batch active learning is to select new observations to be labeled, by an oracle, for training a machine learning model. We present a brief study of a simplified setting in which a single batch of observations (with k matching the associated values in Section 4.3) is selected using only their locations in feature space, after which a random forest classifier is trained on the chosen subset. This setup allows us to isolate the impact of the facility-location objectives on performance. Our results are averaged over 100 random 80/20 train–test splits.

The use of the k -Center objective to bound the loss for active learning was introduced by Sener and Savarese (Sener and Savarese 2018). One motivation for evaluating the k -Median objective of our k -Center solutions is that a simple modification of their proof shows that the k -Median

Table 7 Performance of algorithms on the k -Max-Min-Dispersion objective and the k -Sum-Min-Dispersion objective (normalized so best value equals 1). Larger is better.

Dataset	Method	k -Max-Min-Disp.	k -Sum-Min-Disp.
Iris ($k = 9$)	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	0.994
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.997	1.000
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	0.913
Iris ($k = 18$)	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	0.995
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.871	0.979
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.994	1.000
Heart Disease ($k = 15$)	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	0.990
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.869	0.945
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.988	1.000
Heart Disease ($k = 30$)	Exact k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.881	0.925
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.979	0.983
MNIST ($k = 30$)	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.980	0.994
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
MNIST ($k = 60$)	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.982	0.991
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
CIFAR10 ($k = 30$)	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.970	0.965
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000
CIFAR10 ($k = 60$)	Greedy k -Max-Min-Disp.	0.981	0.991
	Anti-Coverage k -Max-Min-Disp.	1.000	1.000

objective yields an even tighter bound as the average distance to a labeled point is always less than or equal to the largest distance. This tighter bound is presented here as Theorem 1, and the modified proof is provided in the appendix.

THEOREM 1 (Bound on Active Learning Loss). *Given n i.i.d. samples drawn from p_Z as $\{x_i, y_i\}_{i \in [n]}$, and set of points S . If the loss function $l(\cdot; y; W)$ is λ^l -Lipschitz continuous for all y, W (the set of samples trained on), and bounded by L , the training function is λ^μ -Lipschitz, the set S is such that $\delta_i = \min_{j \in S} \|x_i - x_j\|$, $l(x_{S(j)}, y_{S(j)}; S) = 0 \forall j \in S$, and C is the number of values y_i can take; with probability at least $1 - \gamma$:*

$$\left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i \in [n]} \ell(x_i, y_i; S) - \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{j \in S} \ell(x_j, y_j; S) \right| \leq \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i \in [n]} \delta_i \right) (\lambda^l + \lambda^\mu LC) + \sqrt{\frac{L^2 \log(1/\gamma)}{2n}}$$

To this end, we present the results of using the exact optimal k -Median “facilities,” the previously analyzed k -Center algorithms, and a random baseline as the set selected to label, in Table 8.

Table 8 Average Test Set Accuracy Using Different Facility Location Algorithms for Active Learning

Method	Exact k -Center	Exact k -Median	Greedy k -Center	Coverage k -Center	Random
Iris ($k = 9$)	75.40%	84.63%	74.30%	70.87%	71.45%
Iris ($k = 18$)	86.07%	89.43%	82.83%	85.90%	85.22%
Heart Disease ($k = 15$)	70.79%	75.11%	66.89%	68.51%	65.48%
Heart Disease ($k = 30$)	74.36%	77.64%	70.87%	76.87%	74.56%

The results presented in Table 8 raise several noteworthy questions. First, although the exact k -Median solution achieves the highest performance on both datasets, Sener and Savarese report

that heuristic approaches to the k -Median problem underperformed the Greedy k -Center method in large-scale image recognition settings. Second, while the two exact methods exhibit the strongest average performance, the Coverage k -Center algorithm – despite consistently producing solutions with simultaneously superior objective values relative to Greedy k -Center on these tasks – does not appear to empirically dominate Greedy k -Center for the active learning set selection problem, although its average performance is better in three out of four set-ups. These observations suggest that the standard facility-location objectives do not fully characterize the requirements of active learning. Our algorithm is particularly well-suited for further investigation in this direction, as it readily accommodates arbitrary objectives when selecting among candidate test sets. Future research will aim to identify the objective functions that yield the greatest practical benefit.

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Appendix. Proof For Theorem 1 (Adapted from respective proof for k -Center Sener and Savarese (2018))

Before starting the proof, Claim 1 from Berlind and Urner (2015) is provided. Fix some $p, p' \in [0, 1]$ and $y' \in \{0, 1\}$. Then,

$$p_{y \sim p}(y \neq y') \leq p_{y \sim p'}(y \neq y') + |p - p'|.$$

Now start by bounding

$$\mathbb{E}_{y_i \sim \eta(x_i)} [\ell(x_i, y_i; A_s)].$$

By the k -Median version we have that there exists an x_j in the δ_i -ball around x_i such that x_j has zero loss.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{y_i \sim \eta(x_i)} [\ell(x_i, y_i; A_s)] &= \sum_{k \in [C]} p_{y_i \sim \eta_k(x_i)}(y_i = k) \ell(x_i, k; A_s) \\ &\stackrel{(d)}{\leq} \sum_{k \in [C]} p_{y_i \sim \eta_k(x_j)}(y_i = k) \ell(x_i, k; A_s) + \sum_{k \in [C]} |\eta_k(x_i) - \eta_k(x_j)| \ell(x_i, k; A_s) \\ &\stackrel{(e)}{\leq} \sum_{k \in [C]} p_{y_i \sim \eta_k(x_j)}(y_i = k) \ell(x_i, k; A_s) + \delta_i \lambda^\mu LC. \end{aligned}$$

Following the notation of Sener and Savarese, we write $\{y_i = k\} \sim \eta_k(x_i)$ as $y_i \sim \eta_k(x_i)$. Step (d) follows from Claim 1, and step (e) uses the Lipschitz property of the regression function together with the boundedness of the loss. We further bound the remaining term as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k \in [C]} p_{y_i \sim \eta_k(x_j)}(y_i = k) \ell(x_i, k; A_s) &= \sum_{k \in [C]} p_{y_i \sim \eta_k(x_j)}(y_i = k) [\ell(x_i, k; A_s) - \ell(x_j, k; A_s)] \\ &\quad + \sum_{k \in [C]} p_{y_i \sim \eta_k(x_j)}(y_i = k) \ell(x_j, k; A_s) \\ &\leq \delta_i \lambda^l \end{aligned}$$

where the last step uses that the classifier is assumed to have zero loss on training points. Combining the above,

$$\mathbb{E}_{y_i \sim \eta(x_i)} [\ell(x_i, y_i; A_s)] \leq \delta_i (\lambda^l + \lambda^\mu LC).$$

We now apply Hoeffding's Bound and conclude that, with probability at least $1 - \gamma$,

$$\left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i \in [n]} \ell(x_i, y_i; A_s) - \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{j \in S} \ell(x_j, y_j; A_s) \right| \leq \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i \in [n]} \delta_i \right) (\lambda^l + \lambda^\mu LC) + \sqrt{\frac{L^2 \log(1/\gamma)}{2n}}$$

□